

SYNONYMS OF THE LEXEME “CRIME” AND THEIR PECULIARITIES

Gulomova Bibi Mukhlisa Makhmudjon kizi

Student of the faculty of English philology, Teaching methodology and Translation studies,
Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

Supervisor: (PhD) Akhunov Muqumjon Muhammadaminovich

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Abstract. *The present article is dedicated to the semantic analysis of the concept of "crime" in English and Uzbek. This article also reveals the similarities and dissimilarities between the concept of "crime" in English and Uzbek linguocultures. The main, important features of the criminal lexeme should be called the universal nature of the criminal lexeme, which reflects the objective content of the norms, which puts morality above the interests of a narrow group, ideological or practical ideas, corporativeness.*

Keywords: *concept, crime, culture, national culture, linguoculturology, socio-cultural reality, values.*

Determining the conceptual field and semantic field of language seems to be an important and fundamental issue for modern linguistics. In the opinion of many authors, this is interpreted as a "linguistic view of the world" [1,154].

In this scene, “жиноят” in Uzbek, “crime” in English, and “преступление” in Russian concepts also take place as the main concepts of the category of human consciousness. According to E.M. Mikaelyan's candidate's thesis, the concept of "crime" in modern English language discourse is characterized by high representativeness [2,96]. According to the researcher, the concept of "crime" occupies an important place in the linguistic landscape of the modern British and American world (therefore, in society). Also, in Uzbek society, the concept of crime has already begun to gain a different importance in the public consciousness. Evidently, in Europe, there are many cases of criminal acts, violations of the law, killing people, stealing large objects or touching honor. The cited examples are also reflected in movies. Because works are created based on reality. However, it is well known that the British and Americans are strictly following the law as a result of the increasing number of preventive measures and related decisions. Therefore, the crime in the linguistic landscape of the world goes back to the origin of the nation and expresses the reality based on the prism of national and cultural characteristics suitable for a certain group. We can say that people's views on the concept of crime are influenced by their way of life, behavior, social status, mentality, and even their historical past. The individual or collective consciousness embodying objective reality with the help of the function of understanding, knowing the world and thinking about it, understanding, as well as creating and forming ideas, leads to the emergence of universal concepts in the form of concepts.

V.A. Maslova, I.A. Sternin, Z.D. Popova and others. according to his opinion, the concept is described in terms of core and periphery. The core includes layers with the most basic, visually clear, primary, vivid and significant images, while the periphery includes secondary, abstract, associative forms of expression. The main and additional layers are combined in a single basic concept, and the content of the concept is enriched. In the concept of "crime", the lexeme "crime"

is the nucleus, which serves as the only key for naming the concept of "crime". Synonymous and antonymous forms of the lexeme are concepts related to the concept of "crime".

In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the lexeme "crime" is defined as follows: Crime [Arabic-blame, sin; criminal case] 1. law. Violation of the order established by the laws of the state and requiring prosecution under these laws, dangerous behavior for the public. Serious crime. A crime committed using an act. To catch on crime. 2. portable. Harmful behavior, work that leads to bad consequences; sin. *Бас сиз билан биз, Тожибой ака, бу ишга раҳбарлик қилиш ўрнига қўл силтар эканмиз, жиноят қилган бўламиз ва бунинг учун халқ олдида жавобгар бўламиз* [4, 45].

So, the lexeme "crime" is understood in two ways. One is from a legal point of view, and the other is analyzed from a national cultural point of view. According to the first definition, the word "crime" is associated with verbalizers such as law, court, judgment, punishment, accusation, execution, legislation, illegal, code, violation, convict, justice, victim, guilty person.

According to the second definition, a crime in the image of the Uzbek people is considered a great sin. In the teachings of our religion Islam, the concept of crime is divided into big and small sins: 1. Sins between the slave and God Almighty. 2. Sins related to the rights of servants. They include assassination, adultery, bribery, usury, theft, backbiting, lying, slander, obscenity, gambling, drunkenness, embezzlement, etc. includes [3, 63]. In Islam, if a person realizes such a crime, repents and repents, he will be blessed and forgiven by Allah Almighty.

According to "Uzbekistan national encyclopedia": a socially dangerous act provided for in the criminal law. The issue of considering a certain act as J. is decided in each country, taking into account the norms of international law in accordance with its social structure, lifestyle of the population, national characteristics, customs, traditions, etc. An act J. to determine whether the following general signs are taken into account: 1) social danger of the act; 2) presence of guilt; 3) punishability. In any criminal act, all these signs must be present at once, if one of them is not present, there is a reason to consider the act as not J. According to their nature and level of social risk, J.s: not high social risk; not too heavy; heavy; is divided into extremely heavy J. J. against person according to the object of aggression, J. in the field of economy, J. against public security and public order, J. against state power, J. in the field of ecology, J. against the order of military service, J. against peace and security of humanity. is divided by. According to the form of the crime, committed intentionally J. and is divided into J. committed behind negligence. The act of a person is only if he is aware of his action or inaction and the resulting criminal consequences, if he can control his actions J. is considered. Socially dangerous act committed by minors and mentally retarded persons J. is not counted and J. coercive measures provided for in the law cannot be applied. The Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the following 6 types of circumstances that exclude the criminality of an act: 1) minor acts; 2) necessary defense; 3) last necessity; 4) causing harm during the arrest of a person who has committed a socially dangerous act; 5) execution of orders or other tasks; 6) reasonable risk associated with professional or economic activity (Articles 36-41)[4, 254].

So, in the linguistic landscape of the world in the Uzbek language, the concept of "crime" is directly represented by the concept of "sin". In this case, we can look at the concept of "crime" as a "bifurcated concept".

Figure 1. The initial composition of the concept of "crime".

1. Ўзбекистонда ноқонуний молиявий пирамидани ташиқил этган Аҳмадбой ва унинг жиноий шериклари билан боғлиқ суд иши бугун ўз якунига етади. Яъни судья бугун одил ҳукми ўқийди. Ушбу иш Жиноят ишлари бўйича Тошкент вилояти суди томонидан судья Дилишод Комилов раислигида кўрилмоқда [6,19].

2. Ҳали тўзони босилмаган осмонга қараб турган бир чол дўнгилади:
- Бошлаган ишимиз олло таолога ёқмади чоғи. (Саид Аҳмад. Уфқ. 61)

As we can see, the core of the concept of "crime" is the lexeme "crime" and it unites under two concepts. The concept of "sin" is a religious moral concept, which has its own appearance in all religions. It can be considered as a separate concept considering the number of sins and the many related concepts. But it can be seen that its core is crime. Therefore, it is appropriate to use the concepts of crime and sin side by side, that is, the basis of sin is crime, and one of the components of crime is sin. The first part of the crime is an illegal, guilty and wrong socially dangerous act against the laws of the state, and the second part is an act or even an act contrary to Sharia laws and religious beliefs.

In English, the word "crime" is defined in the "Macmillan English Dictionary" as follows:

1. An illegal activity or action: commit a crime (=do something illegal) *She was unaware that she had committed a crime.*

2. Something that is morally wrong or a mistake: be a crime to do sth. *It would be a crime to waste all that food [6, 187].*

In the "ABBYY LINGVO x5" electronic dictionary, the word "crime" is represented by the words transgression, offense, violation, delinquency, criminality, sin, wrongdoing and the following definitions are given:

1. noun

a) an action or omission which constitutes an offence and is punishable by law

b) illegal activities

c) an action or activity considered to be evil, shameful, or wrong.

2. verb [with obj.] (especially in the army) charge with or find guilty of an offence [6, 174].

Turning to the etymology of the word "Crime", according to the "Collins Etymological Dictionary", it is derived from the Latin word *crimen*, which means a charge [7, 88]. The Oxford Etymological Dictionary also states that it was derived from Latin through Old French in the mid-thirteenth century: via Old French from Latin *crimen* 'judgement, offence', based on *cernere* 'to judge' [6, 104]. Яна бир **The Online Etymology Dictionary associates it with the word Sin:** «sinfulness, infraction of laws of God,» from Old French *crimne* «crime mortal sin» (12 c., Modern

French *crime*), from Latin *crimen* (genitive *criminis* «charge, indictment, accusation; crime, fault, offence,» which probably is from *cernere* «to decide, to sift»(from PIE root *krei-*» to sieve», thus «discriminate, distinguish») [7, 5].

- **Conclusion and recommendations (Sonclusion/Recommendation)**. It can be seen that in English, the concept of "crime" is connected with the concept of "sin", and this is represented by the word "gunoh" in Uzbek. The above-mentioned "two-horned concept" means that it is subject to the English language as well. We analyze the concept of "crime" in terms of both legal and linguistic cultural concepts: «*It was such a horrible sin to kill an aged creature like Sam Cayhall. His crimes were committed a generation ago. He had suffered and died many times in his six-by-nine cell. How would the state benefit by killing him now?*» (John Grisham. *The Chamber*, 488)

In E.M. Mikaelyan's candidate's thesis, the concept of "crime" is considered as a tripartite concept. "Srine" includes the violation of human laws, "sin" - divine laws, and "vice" - moral standards. The first of the above will be punished by a court sentence in this world, the second will be punished in the world of the hereafter, and as for the third, he will destroy himself physically and spiritually by indulging in immorality [3, 86]. Yu.G. Evtushok connects the concept of "srine" with the lexemes "sin" and "wrong" and suggests to express it, first of all, as parts of the concept of crime. Secondly, he points out that they can be used as separate concepts and explains: "The analysis of the linguistic expressions of the concepts of crime, sin and wrong shows that these concepts form one field. Their linguistic expressions indicate that they are synonymous. However, it is unlikely that these concepts are completely compatible with each other, each of them has been analyzed by scholars in different ways in the language.

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